

Review

Lysine (K)-deacetylase inhibitors: the real next step to neuropsychiatric and neurodegenerative disorders?

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Abstract

Epigenetic chromatin remodeling and modifications of DNA represent central mechanisms for regulation of gene expression, linking changes in environment, external stimuli, and genetic predisposition to changes in neural function and behavior features, including learning and memory. Lysine deacetylases (KDACs), including classical histone deacetylases (HDACs), play a key role in homeostasis of proteins acetylation such as histones, then regulating fundamental cellular activities like transcription. However, an imbalance in protein acetylation levels and dysfunctions in transcription are associated with a wide variety of brain disorders including neuropsychiatric and neurodegenerative diseases. Treatments with various KDAC inhibitors (KDACis) correct these deficiencies and have emerged as a potential strategy for therapeutic intervention. Indeed, KDACis have neuroprotective, neurotrophic and anti-inflammatory properties, in addition to improve neurological performance, learning/memory and other phenotypes frequently seen in these disorders.

Thus, in this review, it will be discussed the most common epigenetic modifications, how KDACs are classified and regulated, in addition to the mechanisms responsible for interconnect changes in acetylation/deacetylation levels to the onset and/or development of disorders named Bipolar Disorder, Depression, Schizophrenia, Alzheimer's disease, Parkinson's disease and Huntington's disease. Moreover, it will be discussed the pathways underlying the effects of KDAC inhibitors, specifically classes I and II, and why they become the sweetheart of scientific community and clinical trials.

Keywords

Epigenetics, KDAC, KDAC inhibitors, Mood disorder, Schizophrenia, Parkinson disease, Alzheimer disease, Huntington disease.

Abbreviations

3-NP 3-Nitropropionic acid; 5-HT2A 5-hydroxytryptamine 2A; 6-OHDA 6-hydroxydopamine; AD Alzheimer disorder; APP β -amyloid precursor protein; A β β -amyloid peptide; BBB blood-brain barrier; BDNF Brain-derived neurotrophic factor; BP Bipolar disorder; CREB cyclic adenosine monophosphate (cAMP) response element-binding protein; DA dopamine; DARPP-32 Dopamine and cAMP-regulated phosphoprotein with 32 kDa; DNMT DNA methyltransferase; FGF1 Fibroblast growth factor 1; GABA γ -Aminobutyric acid; GDNF Glial cell-derived neurotrophic factor; HAT histone acetyl transferase; HD Huntington disease; Hsp70 Heat shock protein 70; Hsp90 Heat shock protein 90; Htt huntingtin; KDAC lysine deacetylase; KDACi lysine deacetylase inhibitor; mHtt mutant huntingtin; MPP+ 1-methyl-4-phenylpyridinium; MPTP 1-methyl-4-phenyl-1,2,3,6-tetrahydropyridine; NMDA N-methyl-D-aspartate; PB phenylbutyrate; PD Parkinson disorder; PolyQ Polyglutamine; SAHA Suberoylanilide hydroxamic acid; SB Sodium butyrate; SHZ Schizophrenia; TF transcription factor; TSA Trichostatin A; VPA valproic acid; α -Syn α -Synuclein

Introduction

Recent findings implicate epigenetic modifications in the etiology of several brain disorders. Covalent epigenetic modifications of conserved lysine residues in the amino-terminal tails of histone proteins and methylation of DNA control accessibility of chromatin to the core transcriptional machinery and play an essential role in determining the activation state of genes [1-3]. Thus, such modifications alter chromatin structure and make specific regions of the genome more or less accessible to the transcriptional machinery providing a link between environment, genetic predisposition and changes in neural function [1,4-5].

In this review, it will be addressed changes in epigenetics related to histone modifications and how this modification are reflected and related to neuropsychiatric and neurodegenerative disorders. Additionally, it will be discussed how modification in epigenetic can be counteract in order to

induce neuroprotection ameliorating behavioral phenotypes associated to mood disorders (bipolar disorder and depression), Schizophrenia, Alzheimer's disease, Parkinson's disease and Huntington's disease. Along this manuscript, several data using different models are discussed.

Epigenetics

The term "epigenetics" was defined in 1942 to describe molecular events that lead to changes in genetic programs for development [6-7]. However, epigenetics involve heritability, modification of DNA structure without a physical change in the base content and specific alterations in the transcription, resulting in modification of specific phenotypes. Today, epigenetics is accepted as the study of modifications that result in heritable changes in gene expression independent of alterations in DNA sequence [8]. Generally, it is used to define alterations in the structure of chromatin, double-stranded DNA and histones, in which the outcome

is the modification of the transcriptional machinery. In fact, in 2010, the term epigenetics was defined as “the study of molecular signatures that provide a memory of previously experienced stimuli, without irreversible changes in the genetic information” [9]. By packaging DNA and thereby controlling access of other factors to DNA, epigenetic mechanisms provide an important level of regulation of the genome and gene expression throughout development and in post-mitotic cells including neurons.

Histone modification

Histone-induced modifications are post-translational changes in the N-terminal tails of histone proteins that regulate gene expression mainly associated with changes in chromatin structure through several mechanisms named i) phosphorylation, ii) ubiquitination, iii) ADP ribosylation, iv) sumoylation, v) glycosylation, vi) biotinylation, vii) methylation, and viii) acetylation, being methylation and acetylation the most studied. It is important to stress, however, that depending on which histone residue is affected, the same post-translational modification can induce to different effects [10]. As a consequence, chromatin structure can become more “loose” or “tight” facilitating or inhibiting the access of transcriptional machinery to genetic loci (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Representation of histone acetylation and transcription activation. Acetylation of core histone proteins through the activity of histone acetyl transferases (HAT), methylation at K4 by histone methyl transferases (HMT) or treatment with histone deacetylase inhibitors (HDACi) leads to a more open chromatin conformation resulting in a transcription ally active state. On the other hand, removal of acetyl group by HDAC or by methylation on K9 by HMT, repress the transcription after chromatin become more condensate.

Lysine acetylases and deacetylases

Lysine (K) acetylation at the ϵ -amino group is a reversible posttranslational modification that modulates cellular function according to the position of specific lysine residues [11-12], modulating the activity, affinity, stability or protein-protein interactions [13-14]. The fact that histones were identified as the first group of substrates to be acetylated in eukaryotic cells, lysine acetyltransferases and lysine deacetylases, are commonly referred as HATs and HDACs (histone acetyltransferases and histone deacetylases), respectively [11]. However, histones are not the only proteins affected by these post-translational modifications; to date HATs and HDACs are commonly referred (including in this manuscript) as KATs and KDACs (K, lysine). It is important to stress

that considering KDAC non-histone targets, it cannot be generalized that an increase in acetylation will induce an augmentation in transcription. In fact, many non-histone targets seems to be regulated by lysine acetylation named α -tubulin, importin α , heat shock protein 90 (Hsp90) and cortactin [13,15]. Mitochondrial-related proteins also seem to be targets of KATs and KDACs resulting in tighter regulation of metabolism [16]. Thus, lysine acetylation is import not only in transcription, but also in signal transduction and cellular transport processes [13-16].

KDAC enzymes are evolutionarily conserved among many species. In mammals, there are eighteen members of KDAC. A core division based on homology with yeast KDACs separates ‘classical HDACs’ (zinc-dependent) from ‘sirtuins’ (nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide, NAD⁺-dependent). Another division establishes four classes based on phylogenetic analysis and sequence homology to yeast HDACs [17-18]: classes I, II and IV comprise classical HDACs [17], and class III, where it is included sirtuins [19].

Class I KDACs (HDAC1, 2, 3 and 8), homolog of the yeast HDAC RPD3, is constitutively nuclear proteins and is widely expressed in most tissues, except for HDAC8 that is confined to smooth muscle where it associates with α -actin and is essential for contractility [20]. HDAC1 and 2 are highly homologous and act together as the catalytic subunits of transcriptional repressor complexes including Sin3, NuRD/NRD/Mi2, and CoREST [21]. This partnership of KDACs [22] also applies to HDAC3, which is responsible for the deacetylase activities associated with class II KDACs, working together in a repressor complex with SMRT/N-CoR [23]. Class II KDACs is homolog of yeast Hda1 and is expressed in a tissue- and cell-specific manner being highly expressed in the brain, heart, and muscle. Class II is subsequently divided into two subclasses: IIa (HDAC4, 5, 7 and 9) and IIb (HDAC6 and 10), according to their structural similarities. In class IIa, full-length HDAC9 remains in the nucleus, while HDAC4, 5, 7 and a splice variant of HDAC9 (MITR) shuttle between the nucleus and cytosol. Class II is regulated, at least in part, by shuttling between the nucleus and cytoplasm, where they are stabilized by interactions with 14-3-3 proteins. Phosphorylation and binding to 14-3-3 proteins anchor these KDACs in the cytosol, whereas dephosphorylation releases them to return to the nucleus [24]. The class IIb is primarily cytosolic. HDAC6 is unique in containing a C-terminal ubiquitin-binding domain and two functional deacetylase domains. Cytosolic HDAC6 deacetylates tubulin, cortactin and HSP90, regulating axonal trafficking, cell motility and degradation of misfolded proteins [25]. HDAC6 can also shuttle to the nucleus to regulate transcription due to modification in its acetylation status [25]. HDAC10 possesses a unique leucine-rich domain and interacts with HDAC3, resulting in a repression of transcription when fasten to a promoter [26]. In some cases, interactions between different KDAC classes are required to

activate their deacetylase function; for example, HDACs 4, 5 and 7 (class II KDACs) lack the ability to deacetylate histones independently; they require interaction with HDAC3 (class I) to be active [23]. HDAC11, the most recently identified isoform, is a class IV KDAC due to its distinct structure and it is predominantly nuclear, regulating immune tolerance [27].

Differently than classes I, II and IV, class III - sirtuins, has homology to the yeast HDAC Sir2 and encompasses SIRT1–SIRT7 [27]. SIRT1 is located into the nucleus but it was reported to be predominant in the cytosol in the adult brain [28]. SIRT2 is primarily cytosolic although it can be localized in the nucleus, where it preferentially deacetylates histone 4 in the lysine 16 (H4K16) [29]. SIRT2 shares α -tubulin deacetylase activity with HDAC6 [30], and has been suggested as the main microtubule deacetylase in mature neurons [31]. Despite of this data, there is also a report that mentioned that SIRT2 genetic reduction or ablation has no effect on the acetylation of α -tubulin or H4K16 in mouse brain [32]. SIRT6 is a nuclear histone H3K9 deacetylase with a key role in telomere maintenance and DNA repair [33]. SIRT7 is a selective histone H3K18 deacetylase [34] and an activator of RNA polymerase I transcription [35]. SIRT3, 4 and 5 are also called 'mitochondrial sirtuins' due to its subcellular location. SIRT3, the most important mitochondrial deacetylase, regulates oxidative phosphorylation, protein synthesis and multiple metabolic pathways [16]. The other two mitochondrial sirtuins show weak deacetylase activity. Little is known about the activity of SIRT4 and SIRT5 [16].

Lysine (K)-deacetylases inhibitors

The most common KDAC modulator is KDAC inhibitors (KDACis, a.k.a. HDACis), with different structural requirements for acting on classical KDACs or sirtuins. Most classical KDACis, the focus of this review, acts by chelating zinc in the catalytic domain contributing to a non-selective inhibition of distinct isoforms [36]. Differential interaction with amino acid residues at the entry of the KDAC active site is what account for isoform-selective inhibitors, despite little is known about their structure–activity relationships [37–39].

Among the relatively non-selective (Pan-(classical)) KDACis, TSA and SAHA, also known as Vorinostat, are permeable to the blood-brain barrier (BBB) [18,40] and inhibit most zinc-dependent KDACs including HDAC6 in a nanomolar IC₅₀ range [41]. SB and PB, that also cross BBB [42], are fatty acid derivatives that inhibit most class I and II KDACs (Figure 2). However, butyrate does not appear to inhibit HDAC6 because α -tubulin acetylation is not affected [43]. VPA, a fatty acid derivative with mood stabilizing and anticonvulsant properties, is another KDACi that binds to the active site of the enzymes [44–45] and crosses BBB, inhibiting classes I and IIa, but not IIb [21]. Both butyrates and valproate acts in a micro to millimolar range [37]. MS-275,

a synthetic benzamide derivative that also passes BBB, preferentially inhibits HDAC1, compared with HDAC2, 3, and 9, and has little or no activity against HDAC4, 6, 7, and 8 [41]. It seems that MS-275 do not induce any severe side effects. Apicidin, a cyclic tetrapeptide, inhibits HDAC2 and 3 in the low nanomolar range and HDAC8 in the high nanomolar range, but does not affect HDAC1 or class II KDACs [41]. Tubacin shows high selectivity for HDAC6 [46]. Romidepsin (FK-228), another cyclic tetrapeptide, potently inhibits HDAC1 and 2 [47]. It should be noted that the IC₅₀ values of a given KDAC inhibitor for KDAC isoforms varied considerably among different reports.

Figure 2 KDAC isoforms from different KDAC classes and specific and nonspecific inhibitors. Herein is represented the most common inhibitors used in different models of the neuropsychiatric and neurodegenerative disorders discussed in this review.

KDAC inhibitors in neuropathologies

Neuropsychiatric disorders

As expected, along the years epigenetic mechanisms involving chromatin-modifying enzymes and remodeling factors are increasingly implicated in the pathophysiology of mood disorders including bipolar disorder and depression, as well as in other psychiatric diseases such as schizophrenia. For this reason, information regarding epigenetic changes and the role of KDAC to the development of these disorders will be approached. Moreover, studies in which KDACi were used in an attempt to be a disease modifier will be discussed. It is important to point out that chromatin modifications are not static but dynamically change in a cell specific manner during development and in response to external stimuli including neuronal insults.

Mood disorders: Major Depressive Disorder (MDD) and Bipolar Disorder (BPD)

Mood disorders named major depressive disorder (MDD) and bipolar disorder (BPD) are characterized by episodes of depressed mood, diminished interest and hedonic capacity referred to as major depressive episodes [48]. Individuals also present changes in (neuro)vegetative functions as sleep and appetite [48]. Recent evidences from post-mortem brain tissue and lymphocytes patients's revealed alterations in chromatin modification profiles when compared to healthy control subjects. It was demonstrated that the methylation of lysine 9 on histone H3 is reduced in post-mortem brain samples when compared to its control group [49]. It was also described a significant decrease in the expression of several chromatin-modifying enzymes (KDACs or KDMs, *lysine* demethylase) in peripheral blood lymphocytes or post-mortem brain tissue [49-52].

Being MDD a very common disorder [53], novel antidepressants with greater efficacy would serve a large potential patient market. The most part of current antidepressant medications, which increase synaptic levels of serotonin or norepinephrine, has a very slow onset of action. The delay between the administration of an antidepressant and the appearance of therapeutic effects suggests that the elevated synaptic levels of serotonin and norepinephrine must alter other processes before leading to therapeutic effects [54]. In fact, it is suggested that antidepressant interventions involves several adaptative mechanisms (signaling pathways) including neurotrophic factors, stem cell proliferation and differentiation, and epigenetic changes. Regarding to that, it was shown an increase in brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) as a consequence of an augmentation of neurotransmitters levels. Additionally, it was shown that imipramine, a tricyclic antidepressant, and increases histone acetylation at specific promoters of the gene encoding BDNF, in part by reducing levels of HDAC5 in the hippocampus [54]. Thus, the development of therapeutics to target processes upstream of neurotransmitter action, such as KDACs, is a promising area of research. Actually, chronic, but not acute, imipramine reversed the downregulation and overcame hypermethylation of the BDNF locus in response to chronic social defeat stress [54], suggesting that KDACs might function as antidepressants, or effectively enhance the action of existing antidepressants. Recently, Kao and collaborators showed that SB and TSA significantly increased the expression levels of FGF-1B (FGF1, Fibroblast growth factor 1) and that VPA activates FGF1 human gene promoter, which has been shown to regulate cell proliferation, cell division, and neurogenesis through inhibiting KDAC and GSK-3 activities [55]. It was also demonstrated that the KDACi SB improves performance in the tail suspension test, a mouse model of antidepressant efficacy, and enhances the efficacy of the selective serotonin reuptake inhibitor fluoxetine [56]. Resende and colleagues showed that SB reversed the depressive-like and maniac-like behaviors evaluated in an animal model of

depression and maniac, corroborating the data in which SB is suggested as a potential mood stabilizer [57].

Interestingly, a broad range of antidepressants such as imipramine and amitriptyline, two tricyclic antidepressants, along with the selective serotonin reuptake inhibitor paroxetine, were shown to inhibit the activity of DNA methyltransferase (DNMT) DNMT1 in primary rat cortical astrocytes [58]. Instead of a direct effect on the methyltransferase catalytic activity or expression levels of DNMT1, the authors identified euchromatic histone lysine N-methyltransferase 2 (EHMT2), a positive regulator of DNMT1 activity, to be decreased at the level of protein expression [58]. The antidepressant monoamine oxidase (MAO) inhibitor tranylcypromine was shown to inhibit lysine specific demethylase 1 (LSD1) [59].

Recent data indicates that a selective inhibition of HDAC1 and HDAC2 in brain may provide an epigenetic-based target for mood disorders therapeutic [60]. It was demonstrated that systemic treatment with Compound 60 (Cpd-60), a slow-binding benzamide-based inhibitor of HDAC1 and HDAC2 for one week, attenuated locomotor activity following acute amphetamine challenge in mice, in addition to decrease immobility in the forced swim test and increase histone acetylation both globally and at the promoter regions of upregulated transcripts. On the other hand, treatment with SAHA was sufficient to increase histone acetylation in brain, but did not alter mood-related behaviors and had dissimilar transcriptional regulatory effects compared to Cpd-60 [60].

During BPD, an unusually elevated or irritable mood, referred to as manic episodes, can also occurs; when such episodes do not significantly impact functioning, they are considered to be hypomanic episodes. This mood elevation is generally associated with decreased need for sleep, increased physical activity, impulsive as well as goal-directed activity, and pressured speech [48]. Post-mortem studies have revealed altered mRNA and protein expression of HDAC1, 2 and 5 among patients with BPD, but with MDD and schizophrenia (see section 3.1.2. for more details) [51,61-62]. Curiously, electroconvulsive therapy, used in treatment-resistant depression, was shown to alter histone H3 and H4 acetylation at the promoter regions of actively transcribed genes in rat hippocampus [63]. It was also demonstrated that antipsychotic and antidepressants such as valproate, lithium and haloperidol increase histone acetylation in cellular and animal models concomitantly with an improvement of behavioral deficits [64-67]. It was also shown that SB reversed D-amphetamine-induced dysfunction analyzed in prefrontal cortex, hippocampus and striatum of rats, suggesting that Krebs cycle enzymes' inhibition can be an important link for the mitochondrial dysfunction seen in BPD [68]. In fact, many neuropsychiatric and neurodegenerative disorders has, as a main/major cause, mitochondrial dysfunction. Further, HDAC2 was recently demonstrated to be a key

regulator of atypical antipsychotic response [69]. Thus, investigating altered histone acetylation in the context of mood and psychotic disorders may provide insight toward therapeutics.

Following the observation of differential epigenetic state of chromatin in mood disorders, it was observed a decrease in the mRNA profile of HDAC2 and HDAC5 in peripheral white blood cells of depressive individuals [51]. In BPD patients, it was also observed a decrease in HDAC6 and HDAC8 mRNAs accompanied by an increase in HDAC4 mRNA [51]. Since there was no correlation between mRNA expression of any of the KDACs and type of medication (tricyclics, Selective serotonin reuptake inhibitor (SSRI), *Serotonin–norepinephrine reuptake inhibitor* (SNRI), sulpiride, lithium, valproate, and carbamazepine), it was concluded that the alteration of KDAC mRNA expression was unlikely to be due to effects of medication alone [51].

To date, not only nuclear KDACs and TFs are a key role for transcription regulation, but also cytoplasmic HDAC6 emerged in the regulation of affective behaviors [70]. Administration of an HDAC6-specific inhibitor, NCT-14b, had antidepressant-like behavioral effects in the tail suspension test in mice in a manner that was correlated with changes in cytoplasmic tubulin acetylation and could be photocopied by the complete knockout of HDAC6 [70]. In addition, Berton and colleagues have provided additional genetic and pharmacological results further outlining a key role of HDAC6 in regulating stress response and resilience [71].

Schizophrenia (SHZ)

Schizophrenia (SHZ) is a complex, chronic, and heterogeneous psychiatric disorder with high rates of disability, non-recovery, and relapse [72], in which patients present consistent, replicable and clinically significant deficits in cognition [73-74]. In fact, cognitive deficits represent the major characteristic of SHZ affecting approximately 75%-85% of individuals [75-78]. The importance of cognitive deficits in SHZ is emphasized by reports indicating that the severity of cognitive deficits is predictive of treatment compliance, adherence, and risk of relapse among first-episode individuals [79]. Curiously, a pronounced deficit in cognition is frequently reported to be ahead the positive symptoms despite these symptoms persist even after a successful treatment of positive symptoms [80]. Because the symptoms of SHZ do not arise until adolescence and persist, in most cases, throughout life, it has been suggested that this disease may be a neurodevelopmental disorder [81].

The main therapeutics for SHZ are antipsychotics, although the efficacy in ameliorating positive symptoms (delusions, hallucinations, bizarre thoughts) and reducing relapse rates, cognitive deficits and negative symptoms (social withdrawal, poor motivation, apathy) are not sufficient [82-83]. For this reason and due to the fact that cognitive deficits are a risk among individuals with SHZ, the discovery of a novel cognitive therapeutic became appealing [84-85]. However, during the past decade,

a second generation antipsychotics was able to reduce extrapyramidal side effect profiles and to be beneficial on cognitive function [86]. Nonetheless, data are still controversial [87-88].

The heritability of SHZ is reported to be approximately around 70%; though, the presence of risk genes is not sufficient to develop this psychiatric disorder [89]. SHZ is characterized by a complex interplay of genetic susceptibility factors, environmental factors, and randomness factor including epigenetic anomalies [89-90]. Concerning to that, analysis of postmortem brains from patients diagnosed with SHZ or bipolar illness with psychosis showed deficiency in the extracellular matrix protein reelin [91]. Indeed, reelin promoter presents several sites for DNA methylation and inhibitors of KDAC; DNA methyltransferase seems to increase its expression [91]. It was also shown a decrease in the number of gamma-aminobutyric acid-ergic (GABA-ergic) mRNA transcripts including glutamic acid decarboxylase 1 (GAD1), a key enzyme for GABA synthesis, in the prefrontal cortex of humans diagnosed with SHZ [92-93]. Interestingly, these decreases were associated with a diminishing in H3K4 methylation in the GABA-ergic gene loci [92-93].

KDACs have been demonstrated antipsychotic efficacy in addition to facilitate learning and memory and alter synaptic plasticity [69,94-97]. The potential for KDACs as a pharmacological intervention in individuals with SHZ may, in fact, provide insight to disease pathology [94,96,98]. It was shown that MS-275 potently activates GAD1 gene expression in NT2 cells accompanied by decreased GAD1 promoter methylation [99]. On the other hand, it was demonstrated an increase in the methylation levels of H3R17 within a subset of affected patients [100], suggesting that changes in histone modifications at specific genomic loci, rather than on a global scale, may be relevant for gene expression in SHZ. Consistent with this observation, Ac-H3K9K14 levels, two epigenetic marks, were decreased in SHZ patients at the promoter regions of eight SHZ-related genes in 82 postmortem prefrontal cortical samples. These data were in agreement and correlated with gene expression levels for GAD1, 5-hydroxytryptamine receptor 2C (HTR2C), translocase of outer mitochondrial membrane 70 homolog A (TOMM70A) and protein phosphatase 1E (PPM1E) [101]. Additionally, it was demonstrated that treatment with HDACi 4b, a pimelic diphenylamide benzamide-type inhibitor of class I, alters the expression of several candidate genes for SHZ in mouse brain [101].

Recently, Kurita and co-workers demonstrated that metabotropic glutamate 2 (mGlu2) receptors are downregulated by epigenetic chromatin modifications following chronic administration of atypical antipsychotic agents clozapine and risperidone; specifically, induces repressive histone modifications at the promoter region of the mGlu2 gene (also known as GRM2) through a mechanism that involves 5-HT_{2A} receptor-

dependent modulation of the promoter activity of the HDAC2 gene [69]. Chronic treatment with clozapine was accompanied by increased expression and binding of HDAC2 to the mGlu2 promoter, findings that provide a molecular explanation for the decreased acetylation of histone H3 at the mGlu2 promoter in postmortem frontal cortex [69]. This effect, on the opposite, was counteracted by the administration of SAHA or MS-275 [69]. Furthermore, the co-administration of SAHA prevented clozapine-induced down-regulation of mGlu2 and enhanced clozapine's efficacy [69,102]. It was also shown that VPA improves the clinical efficacy of atypical antipsychotic drugs including clozapine, risperidone and olanzapine [103-104].

In addition to HDAC2, Tam and colleagues identified HDAC9 as one of various loci that demonstrated single SHZ-specific deletions after evaluate differences in DNA copy number across the entire genome in 91 individuals with SHZ and 92 controls [105]. A separate study, where was evaluated polymorphisms of KDAC genes among 278 individuals with SHZ and 234 control subjects, indicated that the rs1063639 single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) of the HDAC4 gene was also associated with SHZ in risk models [106].

Neurodegenerative diseases

Excitotoxicity, apoptosis and changes in protein-protein interaction as well as a decrease in protein degradation and modification in transcription regulation have been implicated in the pathophysiology of many neurodegenerative diseases including Parkinson's disease, Alzheimer's disease and Huntington's disease. It is known that KDACs play a key role in homeostasis of protein acetylation and in regulating fundamental cellular activities such as transcription. For this reason, here it will be discussed several treatments with KDACis in different models that are able to counteract these deficiencies, in addition to increase neurotrophins expression, synaptic plasticity and neuronal survival.

Parkinson disease (PD)

Parkinson's disease (PD), which prevalence is estimated to be around 1% of the population over 50 years-old [107], is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder that presents a relatively selective loss of dopaminergic neurons mainly in the substantia nigra pars compacta (SNpc), the mesencephalic brain nucleus responsible for the synthesis of the neurotransmitter, DA [108]. Dopaminergic nigrostriatal pathways project from the SNpc to the striatum, which is responsible for planning and modulation of movement. As a consequence, a disruption of movement and motor based symptoms occur. In fact, PD is characterized by progressive hypokinesia exhibited as slowness of movement, rigidity, development of a resting tremor and loss of postural reflex [109]. Additionally, during disease development, secondary non-motor symptoms also manifest such as dementia, cognitive decline, depression, apathy, sleep disorders, constipation and erectile dysfunction [110].

Several data suggest that apoptosis contributes to neuronal death in PD. In fact, many neurotoxins are used to specifically damage DA neurons and mimic PD named 1-methyl-4-phenyl-1,2,3,6-tetrahydropyridine (MPTP) [111], 1-methyl-4-phenylpyridinium (MPP+), the active metabolite of MPTP, 6-hydroxydopamine (6-OHDA) [112], and rotenone [113], mitochondrial complex I inhibitor. However, once the etiology of PD is not completely understood, many models have been arisen to clarify the different pathways implicated in PD pathogenesis. In addition to neurotoxins, used to understand and correlate apoptosis with mitochondrial dysfunction and oxidative stress [114], studies focused on environmental risk factors, including exposure to metals (copper, manganese, iron), and pesticides [115].

Despite PD is a considered a sporadic disorder, the genetic contribution to PD is significant (10–20%). Indeed, familial PD can take place as a consequence of deficiency in the neuronal protein α -synuclein (α -Syn); intracytoplasmic inclusions composed mainly by α -Syn are one of the most important features of PD [108,116]. The cellular consequences of α -Syn are yet in debate; however associated events such as oxidative stress, inflammation, microglial activation, disruption of axonal transport, synaptic dysfunction, changes in DA availability, inhibition of the ubiquitin proteasome system and multiple organelle dysfunctions are thought to lead rapidly to neuronal death.

To date, no clinical treatment responsible for resting cell death of DA neurons is available; treatments consist in alleviate PD symptoms related to DA dysfunction. The main therapy of PD consists of DA replacement strategies through augmenting the activity of those dopaminergic neurons remaining within the nigrostriatal system. L-Dopa, a precursor in the DA synthetic pathway [117-118], is the most used therapeutic agent. Nonetheless, the usage of DA receptor agonists such as Apomorphine and Pergolide, DA degradation enzyme inhibitors as Catecholamine-o-methyl transferase inhibitor Entacapone and MAO inhibitor Selegiline are often prescribed. Interestingly, none of the current therapies treat non-motor symptoms.

DNA methylation, on contrary of histone post-translational modification, is less transiently dynamic, playing a vital role in longer term repression of gene expression [119-121]. Curiously, the brain has the highest level of DNA methylation in the body despite this equates to just ~1% of nucleic acid bases being methylated [122]. Even though, in sporadic PD patients, it was demonstrated a reduced levels in DNA methylation of intron 1 of the α -Syn gene, SNCA, linking DNA demethylation to α -Syn expression in areas as the SNpc, putamen and cortex [123]. A recent collaborative project identified methylation and changes in expression in three PD risk gene variants (PARK16/1q32, GPNMB and STX1B) in PD patients, indicating that SNCA is not the only hypomethylated gene subjected to altered epigenetic regulation [124]. More recently, it was

observed a reduction in nuclear DNMT1, combined with a translation to the cytoplasm, in post-mortem PD brains as well as in the brains of α -Syn transgenic mice [125]. The maintenance of DNMT1 into the cytoplasm was shown to result in global DNA hypomethylation [125]. Nonetheless, these effects were partially reversed in cell culture and transgenic animal experiments by overexpressing DNMT1, indicating that α -Syn might mediate changes in subcellular localization of DNMT1 in PD [125].

During the last years, KDACi became the focus of several neurodegenerative disorders studies including PD. Recently, it was shown that rats lesioned with 12 μ g of 6-OHDA in the striatum in a two step process (10 μ g/ μ l followed by 2 μ g/ μ l) 48 hours apart exhibited attention set-shifting deficits similar to those observed in PD patients, which was alleviated with SB [126]. Beal and colleagues showed that administration of PB significantly attenuated the depletion of DA and loss of the DA biosynthetic enzyme tyrosine hydroxylase (TH) in the substantia nigra of mice treated with the MPTP [127]. Hong and co-workers demonstrated that MPP⁺-induced death of dopaminergic neurons in an *in vitro* model of midbrain neuron–glia co-cultures was rescued by treatment with VPA, SB or TSA. Moreover, they showed a marked increase in DA uptake and in the number of neurons staining positive for TH [128-129]. Kontopoulos and colleagues showed in *Drosophila* model's that a nuclear localization of α -Syn promoted its toxicity, while its sequestration into the cytoplasm was protective [130]. Specifically, it was shown that α -Syn binds directly to histones, reduces levels of acetylated histone H3, moderates HAT activity, inhibiting HAT-mediated acetyltransferase activity, and interferes with CBP, p300 and P/CAF [130]. Corroborating these data, results showed that administration of KDACis named SB and Vorinostat/SAHA, *in vivo* or *in vitro*, rescued α -Syn-induced toxicity as well as decreased neuronal cell death, suggesting that KDACis may represent a promising therapeutic strategy to mitigate the progressive neurodegeneration linked to PD [130].

Neurotrophic factors such as BDNF and glial cell line-derived neurotrophic factor (GDNF) are a class of neuro-protective compounds that are potentially corrective of damaged DA neurons [131]. Yasuda and colleagues found that BDNF was induced in rat cortical neurons after treatment with VPA, SB or TSA involving activation of BDNF promoter IV [132], and that transfection of siRNA specific for HDAC1 also activated BDNF promoter IV, suggesting a regulatory role of this HDAC isoform in BDNF expression. Additionally, it was shown that VPA, SB and TSA protected DA neurons in a time-dependent manner and up-regulated GDNF and BDNF transcripts in astrocytes. Furthermore, the KDACis lead to marked increases in GDNF promoter activity and promoter-associated histone H3 acetylation in astrocytes [129]. These data reinforce the fact that astrocytes can be an important target for the development of neuroprotective drugs [133-134]; indeed, astrocytes play major roles in

neurotransmission, synaptic plasticity, neurogenesis and secretion of neurotrophic factors [135-138].

Emerging evidence supports the notion that KDACi plays a highly significant role in mediating anti-inflammatory effects in DA neurons. Data show that VPA prolongs the survival of midbrain DA neurons in lipopolysaccharide (LPS)-treated neuron-glia cultures through the inhibition of the release of pro-inflammatory factors from microglia [139-140]. The anti-inflammatory effects were characterized by inhibition of LPS-induced microglial activation, TNF- α release, and nitric oxide production, and were at least partially mediated by triggering apoptosis of overactivated microglia through an induction of mitochondrial dysfunction, specifically due to changes in mitochondrial membrane potential [141]. Similarly, SB was shown to be anti-inflammatory in LPS-treated brain-derived primary microglia [142]. Thus, as evidenced herein, KDACi exerts their neuroprotective effects through different pathways in distinct cell types such as neurons, astrocytes and microglia, indicating that KDACis can have several possible targets to induce neuroprotection.

Despite of all advantages of KDACi treatment to counteract PD, it is important to emphasize that some KDACi have basal toxicity and their prolonged treatment at high doses often induces neuronal death [143]. Wang et al described that TSA induced a decrease in cell survival and increased apoptosis in dopaminergic neuronal cells named rat N27, mouse MN9D and human SH-SY5Y cells [144]. Pre-treatment with TSA resulted in exacerbated neurotoxic damage to dopaminergic neurons induced by MPTP and rotenone, indicating that KDACis may influence PD pathogenesis by inhibiting survival and increasing vulnerability of dopaminergic neurons to neurotoxins [144]. Thus, the KDACi-induced neurotoxicity could be partly due to "derepression" of genes involved in apoptosis including Bim and B-myb [145]. In an effort to side-step these effects, Langley and colleagues found that a two-hour pulse treatment with TSA was sufficient to rescue cortical neurons from oxidative stress without obvious toxicity [146]. Nevertheless, a very recent study showed that class I/II KDACis blocked Bax-dependent apoptosis of mouse cortical neurons by p53-dependent and -independent mechanisms [147].

Alzheimer disease (AD)

Alzheimer disease (AD) is the most common form of neurodegenerative disorder affecting about 50% of the population over 85 years of age in industrialized countries. Clinically, AD is characterized by memory impairments and personality changes, ultimately leading to dementia due to a significant neural degeneration. The earliest stages of AD are characterized by a relatively pure impairment of episodic memory [148]. AD affects primarily the limbic system, particularly the hippocampus and amygdala and, as the disease progresses, neurodegeneration in the temporal and frontal lobes becomes more profound and symptoms worsen [149]. As a result, developing therapeutic strategies

to enhance the encoding, maintenance, and retrieval of memories is critical for improved AD patient outcomes.

Neuropathologically, AD is characterized by the accumulation of extracellular β -amyloid ($A\beta$) peptide, as well as by intraneuronal aggregates of the microtubule-associated protein, Tau, responsible for the formation of neurofibrillary tangles (NFTs) [150-151]. The extracellular plaques are formed through deposits of insoluble $A\beta$ aggregates secreted from neurons. Recently, several studies have shown that soluble oligomers of $A\beta$ are sufficient to cause structural and functional changes to neurons [152-153].

Several environmental factors have been implicated in AD susceptibility. The risk factors include aging, exposure to metals (copper, zinc, mercury, aluminium, lead), solvents, pesticides, dietary deficiencies of vitamin B or folate, systemic infections and inflammation [154]. However, changes in transcription regulation as well as in epigenetics are being correlated to AD. Genetic association studies have identified rare, fully penetrant mutations in three genes: APP, PSEN1, and PSEN2. These mutations are responsible for familial early onset AD, while the majority of AD cases (~95%) are nonfamilial, late-onset sporadic forms [155]. Actually, a number of transgenic mouse models of AD have been generated to mimic amyloidosis and, therefore, familial AD [156-157].

In support for a role of epigenetic mechanisms, abnormal methylation pathways are detected in the brains of people afflicted with dementia, including late AD onset; and these changes are detectable much earlier than the pathological and clinical features. The levels of S-adenosyl methionine, which is required for the methylation of both DNA and histones, are decreased in late AD onset [158]. A decrease in DNA methylation was observed by Mastroeni and co-workers in the entorhinal cortex, a region exhibiting substantial AD pathology [159]. However, Silva and colleagues reported significant hypermethylation of human telomerase reverse transcriptase (hTERT) gene and this resulted in increased expression rather than the unusual silencing in histopathological studies in AD subjects [160]. Additionally, several studies identified epigenetic mechanisms acting on genes related to the $A\beta$ pathway. It was demonstrated that the gene encoding neprilysin, which is the major $A\beta$ degrading enzyme and whose expression is decreased in both Alzheimer's and aging brains, is methylated under the very influence of $A\beta$ itself [161]. Curiously, accordingly to this work, the production of $A\beta$ induces silencing of the gene responsible for its removal resulting in more $A\beta$ production [161]. Another study, using different cell lines, suggests the regulation of the neprilysin gene by histone modifications rather than DNA methylation [162] emphasizing the complexity of epigenetic mechanisms in AD.

Recent experimental studies suggest that changes in histone acetylation are associated

with AD pathology. In fact, Peleg and colleagues showed that deregulation of histone acetylation is associated with age-dependent memory impairment [163]. The group demonstrated that aged mice (16-month-old C57BL/6 strain) bare a specific alteration of histone H4 lysine12 (H4K12) acetylation and this defect down-regulates hippocampal gene expression associated with memory coalition. Accordingly, it is known that the reduction in the levels of histone acetylation by preventing HAT activity promotes amnesia and interferes with the consolidation of hippocampus-dependent memories [164-166]. Data also suggest that the intracellular tail fragment of APP cleavage by γ -secretase could recruit the nuclear adaptor protein Fe65 and the HAT Tip60, resulting in an increase in the transcription [167-169]. On the other hand, an inhibition of KDACs by SB, which artificially increases the acetylation and transcription of some genes, enhanced hippocampus-dependent memory formation and the induction of hippocampal LTP at Schaffer-collateral synapses in area CA1 [166,170]. In agreement with this hypothesis, preclinical studies with APP/PS1 mouse model of AD, double transgenic for APP and PS1, showed that acute treatment with TSA, prior to training (fear conditioning), rescued both acetylated H4 levels and contextual freezing performance to wild-type values and rescued CA3-CA1 LTP in slices from APP/PS1 mice [171]. Interestingly, SAHA treated mice accumulate acetylated H4K12 and improve learning associated gene expression [163].

Accordingly with the data mentioned previously, the role of histone-tail acetylation in memory formation and plasticity is also supported by other several studies. In APP^{swe}/PS1^{dE9} mice, a double transgenic mice (PP/PS1 with strain name B6C3-Tg (APP^{swe}, PSEN1^{dE9})85Dbo/J), a chimeric mouse/human APP transgene that contains the Swedish mutations (K595N/M596L) as well as a mutant human PS1 transgene carrying the deleted exon 9 variant under control of mouse prion promoter elements, chronic KDACi injections (2–3 weeks) of sodium valproate, SB or SAHA did not alter contextual memory formation in normal mice, but had profound effects in transgenic animals [172]. Further behavioral testing of the KDACi-treated transgenic mice showed that the newly consolidated memories were stably maintained over a 2-week period. Measurement of the KDAC isoforms after treatment with sodium valproate, SB and SAHA revealed the common inhibition of class I KDACs (HDAC1, 2, 3, 8), suggesting that this class is a promising target to treat cognitive deficits associated with early stage AD [172]. Additionally, it has also been reported a significant decrease in acetylation status of H4 in older APP/PS1 mice, but not when animals were 6-months of age. As observed previously, administration of several KDACis (e.g. sodium valproate or SAHA) induced expression of acetylated histone H4 and transcription of target genes and improved hippocampus-dependent memory formation [172]. In APP23 transgenic AD

mice, daily injections with a relatively low dose of VPA (30 mg/kg, i.p.) reduced A β plaque number and improved memory deficits when administered early (starting at seven months) due to inhibition of GSK-3 β -mediated γ -secretase cleavage of APP [173]. Interestingly, GSK-3 β , which activity protects the cell from the neurotoxic actions, seems to directly phosphorylate HDAC3, a KDAC that show a strong neurotoxic effect and a cellular specificity [174]. Recently, McQuown and Wood investigated the effect of HDAC3 in learning and memory [175]. The data generated demonstrated an increase in histone acetylation, a significant improvement in long term memory in the novel object recognition task and increased expression of the genes of nuclear receptor subfamily 4, group A, member 2 (Nr4a2), and c-Fos, implicated in long-term memory. The importance of HDAC2 to AD was also demonstrated. It was shown that the knockdown of HDAC2 results in increased synapse number and memory facilitation, while the overexpression of HDAC2 decreased dendritic spine density, neuronal synaptic plasticity and memory formation, features that were ameliorated by SAHA [176]. HDAC6 is also associated to AD. HDAC6 is linked to both microtubule and actin-dependent cell motility through modulation of the acetylation levels of α -tubulin and F-actin-binding protein [177], respectively, and also deacetylates Hsp90 and is a component of aggresome complex. Ding and co-workers not only described the connection between HDAC6 and Tau protein, but also that TSA did not interfere with communication between HDAC6 and Tau, but delayed Tau phosphorylation [178]. More recently, it was also revealed that Tau prevents induction of autophagy by inhibiting proteasome function and increases tubulin acetylation by binding and decreasing the activity of HDAC6 [179].

In Tg2576 AD mice, a mouse model that expresses the human 695-aa isoform of APP containing the Swedish double mutation (APP^{swe}) [(APP695)Lys670 \rightarrow Asn, Met671 \rightarrow Leu], PB treatment reversed spatial memory deficits by normalizing *Tau* hyperphosphorylation in the hippocampus without affecting A β levels [180]. PB treatment also ameliorated the dramatic loss of histone H4 acetylation in the cortex and promoted GluR1, PSD95 and MAP2 expression, suggesting that the underlying neuroprotective mechanisms involve normalization of transcriptional dysfunction [180]. Interestingly, in neuronal cultures from Tg2576 mice, it was observed a correlation between histone 3 acetylation and decreased phosphorylated Tau levels. PB treatment notably increased expression levels of plasticity-related proteins such as the *N*-methyl-D-aspartate (NMDA) receptor subunit, NR2B, and the synaptic scaffold protein, SAP102 [181]. Moreover, in Tg2576 neurons treated with PB, but not with SB, it was shown a decrease in the processing of the APP. Curiously, in Tg2576 mice treated with PB or SB for 3 weeks, only PB normalized the pathological AD markers, implicating, at least in part, other mechanism as the chaperone-like activity

[182]. Furthermore, treatment with PB but not SB, prevented the neuronal loss in the hippocampus of hAPPWT-overexpressing mice, particularly evident in the CA1 layer. Thus, in addition to its activity as a KDACi, the chaperone activity of PB appears to at least partially mediate its reversal of the AD phenotype in Tg2576 mice and its neuroprotective effect in a model of hippocampal neuronal loss [182].

Different mechanisms regarding to neuroprotection in cell model of AD demonstrate the broad range of KDACis. In cultured primary cerebellar granule cells and during signal activation of APP in cultured primary cerebral cortical neurons from rodents, it was observed a decrease in the HATs CBP/p300 and histone protein acetylation during apoptosis induced by potassium deprivation [183]. On the other hand, when an overexpression of CBP/p300 was induced, a neuronal protection in these neurons was observed [183]. In HEK293 cells expressing Swedish APP and in the brains of APP transgenic mice, VPA appears to decrease A β production [184]. Furthermore, in cultured cortical neurons, Ryu and colleagues showed that treatment with TSA, SB or SAHA protected against glutathione depletion-induced oxidative stress; the pathway for neuroprotection involved acetylation and activation of the DNA binding activity of Sp1 [185].

Huntington's disease (HD)

Huntington's disease (HD) is a fatal autosomal dominant neurodegenerative disease and the most common polyglutamine (polyQ) disorder [186-187, for review]. HD is a typical adult-onset disorder with a low prevalence (3-10 affected subjects per 100,000 individuals) [186-187, for review], characterized by a biphasic progression of motor deficits, an initial chorea (irregular, unpredictable, and involuntary muscle jerks) and bradykinesia, that culminate in rigidity and hypokinesia [188]. In the majority of HD cases, the disease manifests in midlife (between 35 and 50 years of age) being fatal 15-20 years after the initial symptoms [189-190]. Other clinical features include progressive cognitive decline and dementia, emotional impairment and psychiatric manifestations (depression, irritability, apathy) and seizures [191, for review].

HD, a pure genetic disorder, was firstly described by George Huntington in 1872. However, the mutation in the HD gene was only discovered in 1993 by Gusella and Macdonald [192]. The mutation consists of an unstable expansion of CAG repeats (>35) within the coding region of the HD gene (containing 67 exons and located in the short arm of chromosome 4 (4p16.3)), which encodes huntingtin (Htt), a protein of approximately 350 kDa. As a consequence, a stretch of glutamine residues arises at the N-terminal of Htt [193]. There is an inverse correlation between CAG length and disease onset particularly for the largest CAG repeats [194-195]. However, this implicates that HD carriers with CAG repeats between 40 and 50 have other factor rather genetic that may play an important role in HD pathology.

Neuropathologically, despite the ubiquitous expression of mutant Htt (mHtt), HD is characterized by typical and selective neuronal atrophy of striatal medium-sized spiny neurons (95% of the striatal neuronal population), leading to a primarily degeneration of caudate nucleus and the putamen [196], the primarily reason for the decline in cognitive performance [197]. HD involves accumulation of striatal and/or cortical intranuclear inclusions and protein aggregates in dystrophic neurites [198] and, therefore, HD also affects cerebral cortex. Although intranuclear inclusions show a positive correlation with the length of CAG repeat expansion, they do not predict neuronal death [199-200]. Curiously, a specific neuronal population in the hypothalamus is affected in HD [201-204].

Numerous pathological mechanisms have been postulated in HD, including protein aggregation, decreased neurotrophic support, excitotoxicity, DA toxicity, oxidative stress, apoptosis, autophagy, altered calcium (Ca^{+2}) handling, proteasome inhibition, mitochondrial dysfunction and transcription deregulation [205-206, for review]. All these mechanisms can occur in parallel promoting each other.

Concerning to transcription deregulation, it is known that mHtt affects the expression of key metabolic enzymes and proteins, may function to disrupt coactivator complexes on susceptible gene promoters [207] and interferes with TF activity [208]. In this respect, it is known that polyQ repeats at the N-terminal region of Htt protein have structural similarities to known TFs [209] thus modulating its activity namely CREB, TATA-binding protein (TBP), p53 and Sp1, a neuroprotective TFs, and its co-activator TAF 130 [210-214]. Additionally, mHtt, contrary to wild-type Htt is distributed predominantly within the cytoplasm and, once cleaved by calpain and caspases, translocates to nucleus where sequesters TFs and nuclear acetyltransferases [215].

Despite DNA methylation is the most studied epigenetic so far, epigenetic changes in terms of DNA methylation in HD are just beginning to be studied [216]. In fact, it was described recently that there are changes in DNA methylation in HD patients and HD transgenic mice [216-218]. Ng and co-workers [216] showed that the promoter regions of the Ap-1, Sox2, Pax6, and Nes genes are highly methylated, and that expression levels of these genes are significantly reduced. Because these genes are directly involved in neurogenesis, changes in hippocampal function and cognitive decline in HD can be linked to impairment in DNA methylation. But it is still a big question mark how mHtt triggers DNA methylation and which DNMTs and DNA methylation maintenance factors are directly or indirectly involved in abnormal epigenetic modifications. It was discovered a novel epigenetic pathway whereby trimethylated histone H3K9 (H3K9me3)-dependent heterochromatin condensation leads to transcriptional deregulation of muscarinic

acetylcholine (ACh) receptor 1 (CHRM1) by occupying its promoter in HD striatal cells [219]; it is known that CHRM1 promotes phosphatidylinositol hydrolysis and intracellular Ca^{+2} mobilization [220-223]. The CHRM1 is highly expressed in the striatum of control brain, while is down regulated in HD striatum [220,224-225]. Interestingly, a deregulation of striatal cholinergic system has been suggested in the pathophysiology of HD. Data indicate that loss of cholinergic receptor function directly results in synaptic dysfunction through inadequate intracellular signal transductions in neurons, a predicted consequence if consider that CHRM1 is a major muscarinic receptor transducing intracellular Ca^{+2} signaling; the reduction of CHRM1 protein levels result in the deregulation of intracellular Ca^{+2} release from endoplasmic reticulum in response to ACh in HD striatal cells [219]. Because ACh plays a key role in the regulation of striatal output by influencing the activity of GABA-ergic medium spiny neurons, the interaction of ACh with pre- and post-synaptic CHRMs is pivotal to modulate the striatal activity. Also, it has been shown that the adenosine A (2A) receptor (A2AR) is markedly reduced in HD, but regulation of the A2AR gene (ADORA2A) expression is not known in HD [217]. A recent study shows that while the reduction of A2AR is correlated with increased levels of 5-methylcytosine in the 5'-UTR region of ADORA2A gene in the striatum of HD patients, A2AR down-regulation is correlated with a reduction of 5-hydroxymethylcytosine in the 5'-UTR region of the ADORA2A gene in HD transgenic mice [218].

Many other evidences co-relate DNA methylation alterations with HD. The condensation of H3K9me3-dependent heterochromatin structure has been shown to be a prominent pathological feature of HD. It was shown that the levels of SETDB1 protein, ERG-associated protein with SET domain (ESET), and H3K9me3 are elevated in striatal neurons of HD patients and HD transgenic animal models [226], suggesting that neuronal levels of SETDB1 and H3K9me3 may be predictive markers of nucleosomal dysfunction in HD [227]. Consistent with this, altered expression of HMT and elevated H3K9me3 are linked to upstream transcriptional deregulation in both animal models of HD and in HD patients [226,228-229]. Thus, the increase of H3K9me3 level has been correlated gene silencing in both global and local repression of transcription [230-231].

CBP plays a role as a HAT in acetylating histones that contribute to transcription by remodeling the chromatin structure [232]. Importantly, it has been known for more than a decade that sequestration of CBP by mHtt leads to neuronal transcriptional dysfunction [211,233] and causes the hypermethylation and hypo-acetylation of histone proteins [226,228,234-236]. The polyglutamine stretches in mHtt interact physically with CBP and block its transcriptional co-activator function as well as intrinsic CBP KAT activity [210-211]. CBP interacts with diverse TFs and with components of the RNA polymerase II complex, thereby acting

as a co-activator or repressor of transcription. A loss of CBP function interferes with transcription by inhibiting recruitment of the basal transcription machinery to the promoter and by altering the acetylation level of histones and chromatin structure in neurons [164-165]. Indeed, Korzus and colleagues demonstrated that the stabilization of short-term memory into long-term memory is impaired in transgenic mice expressing CBP that lacks HAT activity, whereas acquisition of new information and short-term memory is spared [165]. Concomitantly, p300 mutant mice lacking carboxy-terminal HAT and activation domains have impaired long-term recognition memory and contextual fear memory [237]. Moreover, Oliveira and colleagues [237] demonstrated that p300 is required for certain forms of memory, and that the HAT and carboxy-terminal domains play critical roles.

Many changes observed in HD results from transcription deregulation due to histone hypo-acetylation, which leads to down regulation of genes. However, therapeutic inhibition of KDAC seems to restore the acetylation level of histone improving the neuropathology and the motor symptoms [233,235-236,238-239]. Of the five classes of KDAC inhibitors, butyrates are the most developed for clinical use, and their bioavailability in the central nervous system is known. SB modulates epigenetic histone modifications, improves motor performance, gross brain weight and atrophy, and striatal neuron atrophy, delaying the neuropathological sequelae, and significantly extends survival of R6/2 transgenic mouse model, which express an N-terminal portion of human htt with 150 or more polyglutamine repeats, in a dose-dependent manner (up to 20.8%) [234]. SB also increased histone H3 and H4 and Sp1 acetylation in addition to protect against 3-nitropropionic acid (3-NP, a selective and irreversible inhibitor of mitochondrial complex II) neurotoxicity [226,234]. SB also seems to be protective by improving transcriptional regulation, resulting in an increased expression of proteins involved in transcription and metabolism [234]. The great advantage of this compound is its low toxicity and the fact that is well tolerated in both human and animal studies [240-242]. PB is metabolized to phenylacetate that possesses KDAC inhibitory activity and shows high levels of brain bioavailability [243]. PB is a feasible compound for testing in HD because it is Food and Drug Administration approved and there is a preponderance of pharmacokinetic, toxicity, and available dosing information available. Sadri-Vakili and colleagues demonstrated that despite no change in overall acetylated histone levels, histone H3 is hypo-acetylated at promoters of downregulated genes in R6/2 mice, ST14a and STHdhQ111 cells and in clonal striatal cell lines from HD knock-in mice expressing 111 glutamines [235]. In addition, PB increased association of acetylated histones with downregulated genes and corrects mRNA abnormalities. In contrast, there is a decrease in mRNA levels in wild-type cells following treatment with a histone acetyltransferase

inhibitor. It was shown that administration of PB in N171-82Q mice model post-symptomatic (at 11 weeks), which contains a truncated human *HD* gene under the control of the mouse prion promoter and expresses a peptide with 171 amino acids and 82 glutamines [244], remodels chromatin structures and improves neuropathological phenotype observed [228]. Moreover, PB increased brain histone acetylation, mRNA for glutathione-S-transferase and components of the ubiquitin-proteasome system, and decreased histone methylation levels and caspase-9 levels, implicated in the intrinsic pathway of apoptotic cell death [228]. However, PB in this mouse model failed to improve rotarod performance or the increase in body weight [228].

SAHA, in addition to SB, was the first compound that provided the efficacy of KDAC inhibition and histone modification in HD transgenic mice [245-246]. Enhancement of memory formation was found in mice treated with SAHA or SB, or, interestingly, subjected to genetic knockout of the HDAC2 gene [246]. Hockly and co-workers [245] demonstrated that SAHA, that partially crosses BBB, was able to increase histone acetylation in R6/2 mice brains and to improve motor function in rotarod analysis. Nevertheless, SAHA did not ameliorate the failure to gain weight in R6/2 mice, did not affect polyQ aggregation or down regulated the expanded mHtt in the R6/2 mice, and high doses were shown to be toxic [245]. Curiously, prolonged SAHA treatment was shown to cause the degradation of HDAC4 in cortex and brain stem, but not hippocampus, without affecting its transcript levels *in vivo* [245]. Mielkcarek and colleagues [246] found that SAHA reduces SDS-insoluble aggregate load in the cortex and brain stem but not in the hippocampus of the R6/2 brains, opposing part of the results demonstrated by Hockly's group [245]; interestingly, this results was accompanied by restoration of BDNF cortical transcript levels. McCampbell and co-workers showed that polyglutamine decreases histone acetylation, while SAHA and TSA reduced polyglutamine induced toxicity in R6/2 mice [247]. In addition, the authors demonstrated that cell death could be reduced by over-expression of full-length cAMP. Although changes in histone acetylation correlate with decreased gene expression, histone hypo-acetylation may be a late event, as no hypo-acetylation is observed in 4-week-old R6/2 mice [247]. Treatment with SAHA and SB also suppressed ongoing neuronal photoreceptor degeneration and reduced lethality in transgenic *Drosophila* expressing mHtt [233]. Another report showed that neurodegeneration was sensitive to the zinc-dependent fly HDAC Rpd3 in a *Drosophila* model [248]. Bates and co-workers demonstrated that in *Caenorhabditis elegans* HD model the knockdown of hda-3 suppressed neurodegeneration in response to mHtt-Q150 (150 glutamines) [249]. On the other hand, deletion of one copy of hda-1 enhanced polyQ neurotoxicity, suggesting that these two KDAC isoforms act on different targets to induce opposite effects on polyQ toxicity.

Thomas and co-workers [250] described a new compound, a benzamide-type KDAC inhibitor, pimelic diphenylamide HDAC inhibitor 4b (HDACi 4b), which more selectively inhibited HDAC1 and HDAC3. Chronic oral administration of HDACi 4b, that is more selective for HDAC1 and HDAC3, before the onset of motor deficits in symptomatic R6/2 mice, significantly improved motor performance, overall appearance and body weight [250]. For selected genes, HDACi 4b treatment reversed histone H3 hypoacetylation observed in the presence of mHtt, and corrected mRNA expression levels. At a molecular level, the authors found changes in gene expression of a limited number of genes, rather than global effects [250]. It was also shown that HDACi 4b significantly prevented body weight loss, improved several parameters of motor function and ameliorated Htt-elicited cognitive decline in N171-82Q mice, data that was co-related to prevention in the formation of nuclear Htt aggregates in the brains and with the modulation of the ubiquitin-proteasomal and autophagy pathways [251]. Interestingly, HDACi 4b treatment modulated gene networks involving post-translational modification, including protein phosphorylation and ubiquitination pathways [251]. Data from the same group also revealed that HDACi 4b and 136, both compounds showing high potency for inhibiting HDAC3 were most effective in reversing the expression of genes relevant to HD, including Ppp1r1b, which encodes DARPP-32. In contrast, compounds targeting HDAC1 were less effective at correcting gene expression abnormalities in R6/2 transgenic mice, but did cause significant increases in the expression of selected genes. In a *Drosophila* model of HD and in STHdhQ111 striatal cells, the results suggested that inhibition of HDACs 1 and 3 could relieve HD-like phenotypes in model systems and that KDAC inhibitors targeting these isoforms might show therapeutic benefit in human HD [252]. Subsequent reports provided an intriguing explanation for the efficacy and well-tolerated effects of the HDACi 4b. A common feature of these KDACi is an acylated ortho-phenylene diamine unit, which is thought to interact with the zinc ion of KDACs. Compounds from this series are selective for HDAC1, HDAC2, and HDAC3 over other KDAC isoforms, with no activity reported against KDAC class IIa enzymes and only weak activity reported against HDAC8 [253-254]. Furthermore, they appear to bind to the catalytic site of these KDACs via a unique binding mode not shared with other hydroxamic acid based inhibitors; a time-dependent increase in affinity with an extremely slow off rate has been observed [254-256].

The transcriptional factor complex repressor element-1 TF (REST)/neuron-restrictive silencer factor (NRSF) is also affected in HD as it is less bound by mHtt (compared to wild-type Htt) in the cytoplasm; consequently, unbound REST is liberated to translocate into the nucleus, where it binds to the neuron-restrictive silencer element (NRSE) present in the promoter of the BDNF gene,

repressing its expression [257]. Regarding to that, it has been suggested that the pathophysiology of HD is intimately coupled to BDNF and also HSP70 deficiency [258-260]. Since both BDNF and HSP70 expression is regulated by class I and II KDAC inhibitors. It was hypothesized that restoring BDNF and HSP70 to their normal levels, HD feature would be also ameliorated. In this context, SAHA and TSA, but not PB or MS-275, increased vesicular transport of BDNF by inhibiting HDAC6 and, thereby, increasing tubulin acetylation and compensating for the transport deficit in HD [261]. However, the role of HDAC6 in HD pathology is complex. HDAC6-dependent retrograde transport on microtubules is crucial for autophagic degradation of aggregated Htt [262]. Moreover, expression of HDAC6 rescues polyQ-induced neurodegeneration associated with dysfunction of the ubiquitin-proteasome system in a fly model of spinobulbar muscular atrophy [263]. The dual roles of HDAC6 in neurodegeneration and neuroprotection complicate the application of this subtype-specific inhibition in treating polyQ-induced neurodegenerative diseases.

Conclusion and Future perspective

Along this manuscript, it was described *in vivo* and *in vitro* evidences supporting changes in DNA methylation and/or histone modifications associated with transcriptional dysfunction, both in neuropsychiatric and neurodegenerative disorders. Experimental data suggest that treatment with KDACis (Class I and II) ameliorate these deficiencies in addition to induce neuroprotection, improve neurological performance and ameliorate behavioral phenotypes related to depression, BP, SHZ, AD, PD and HD. KDACis beneficial effects are achieved through different pathways increasing histone acetylation, mitochondrial function, neurotransmission and neurotrophic factor, modulating autophagy, and decreasing cell death (Figure 3). Interestingly, some of the KDACis targets are common between neuropsychiatric and neurodegenerative disorder, as shown. Thus, one can speculate if the data obtained in a specific neuropathology model, can be extrapolated to another increasing, as a consequence, the knowledge and the percentage of success discovering new therapies.

KDACis not only act on neurons, but also in other cell types of the nervous system as astrocytes and microglia, suggesting that glia is also an important target for therapeutic intervention. In addition to transcriptional regulation, non-transcriptional events, such as improvement of microtubule stability via enhanced acetylation, have been implicated in the neuroprotection and neuronal stability. Hence, the relation between epigenetic and neuropathologies are open for further study of mechanisms underlying disease development and progression.

Figure 3KDACis main cellular effects in neuropsychiatric and neurodegenerative disorders. KDACi can act in different pathways related to mitochondrial function, cell death, neurotransmission, protein degradation and amount of neurotrophic factor. Interestingly, some of the KDACis targets are common between neuropsychiatric and neurodegenerative disorder, as shown in the picture.

However, up to now it is unknown if pan-KDACi or some isoform-specific KDACi would be more efficacious in treating any given disease. Nonetheless, it is important to stress that the development of potent and effective KDACi has to prioritize an excellent BBB permeability and low cytotoxicity, which remains a major challenge. KDACi toxicity should be tested in all experimental study to standardize its effect concerning the dosage and the duration of the treatment in a specific cell type and animal model avoiding, as a consequence, misunderstanding and misinterpretation of the results obtained. In fact, it is very often different results with the same KDACi but in different models. Furthermore, KDACi is not able to target exclusively the brain [106]; in reality, this can be the major reason for side effects of KDACis treatment.

Acknowledgements

TRR acknowledges support by *Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia*(FCT), Portugal, project SFRH/BPD/44246/2008.

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